

CONCEPT OF ENGAGEMENT AND MOTIVATION IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE CLASSES

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Abstract:

The article explains the conceptual foundations of student engagement and motivation by examining their interrelationship in foreign language classrooms. Depending on existing research and theories, including Self-Determination Theory, educational and instructional approaches, the study investigates three dimensions of engagement related to emotional, behavioural, and cognitive processes, and intrinsic and extrinsic motivation. Furthermore, it highlights practical pedagogical styles, such as, peer working and competence-based learning, which integrated with online educational games and guided by teacher's role can improve learners' autonomy and participation level in the teaching context.

Keywords: Student engagement, intrinsic and extrinsic motivation, Self-Determination Theory, teachers' role, foreign language learning.

Introduction

Teaching English as a foreign language for more than a decade, student engagement and motivation in classes are still one of the discussable parts of the language teaching process. As digital education and technologies are becoming endemic, the community of educators needs to find effective ways to keep their learners motivated and engaged. So, carefully planned and designed game elements can be extremely useful in promoting motivation, which can definitely influence students' future results later [Shakhnoza Ismailovna Nurmatova, 2025:303].

The Concept and Dimensions of School Engagement

School engagement, defined as the degree of students' participation, emotional attachment, and sustained commitment to academic and social activities within the educational environment, plays a critical role in preventing academic underachievement, fostering competence, and shaping a wide range of adolescent developmental outcomes. Although, the multidimensional nature of school engagement is widely recognized, the mechanisms underlying the interactions among its three core components remain insufficiently explored. However, these three dimensions of engagement can be defined as behavioural -focusing on student participation in different educational, social, and out-of-lesson activities, which is very essential for academic improvement and consistency. As for emotional engagement, it refers to students' reactions towards teachers, friends, tasks, and school territory that can promote a sense of belonging to this community. Cognitive engagement requires investment of students' effort, mental awareness, and readiness to learn complex strategies. It is believed that behavioural and emotional engagement are reciprocally related, with each construct serving as both a predictor and an outcome of the other. Furthermore, behavioural engagement significantly influences cognitive engagement, while the reverse relationship has not been supported by empirical evidence [Fredricks et al., 2004:60; Li & Lerner, 2013:20-32; Yang et al., 2021]. Student engagement and classroom interaction are multidimensional constructs, with each dimension being interrelated and mutually influential. Emotional engagement is positively associated with behavioural engagement, and both emotional support and instructional support mediate the relationship between emotional and behavioural engagement [Yang Yu., Yuan Yu., Tan H., Wang Y., & Li G., 2021:512-525].

The Role of Motivation in the Educational Process

Besides that, a lack of motivation in education can make learning more difficult. Both students and teachers are motivated in different ways, which makes the educational environment dynamic. Teachers help create a positive atmosphere that encourages learning and long-term success. While students contribute by staying active and focused on understanding the material to improve their academic performance. So, building strong communication and collaboration between students and teachers is also important for motivation [Vero & Puka, 2017:57-66].

Social Context and Types of Learners

According to [Toshalis E., & Nakkula M ,2012], student motivation can be different based on what kind of social context students come from. We have to know our students' social worlds, which can affect our efforts in the classroom. For example, some students enter school with supported academic achievement and are full of motivation for learning; they do not expect any extra attention or favour from their teachers; instead, they are ready for the offers that will be given by the teacher. As we call them "pre-motivated" learners who are always welcomed by their fellows and the school administration because of their behaviour and good participation during the classes. Usually, these students' achievements are the result of family support, parental motivation, beliefs, and student culture, which can reinforce positive self-image and create future opportunities for them, however, other students head to school with quite different attitude. Their social situation, more precisely, the background of their family, immigration status, and linguistic contrasts, and others, can marginalize their ability and mark them differently as "other". For these kinds of students, engagement can be needed in order to achieve motivation [Toshalis & Nakkula, 2012:9]. The comparisons of these students clarify three essential aspects of motivation and its connection to engagement. First, there is no motivation and engagement type that can guarantee learners' academic achievements regularly. Because of having different life-pathways and stories, everyone may express and demand needs in different ways. Therefore, instead of always organizing the same homogeneous classrooms at school, differentiating instructions and individual approach can work better [Lawrence-Brown, 2004:1-62; Santamaria,2009]. Second, the function of motivation and engagement can be separately understood depending on the students and their conditions. For instance, some learners need motivation to be engaged, yet others are already motivated without being engaged. In short, motivation and engagement can be interrelated concepts or vice versa. Third, psychological factors, namely, feeling welcomed into or encouraged by school officials, can have a huge impact on students' better participation and motivation level [Toshalis & Nakkula, 2012:3].

Types and Orientation of Motivation in Self-Determination Theory

During the empirical period, several types of motivation were witnessed and classified by various scientists. In this regard, people may differ not just in how much motivation they have, but also in the type of motivation they possess. It is called "level" of motivation, which deals with the "amount" of motivation that people have, and "orientation" of motivation, which concerns internal and external factors that can urge people to act forward. In turn, orientation of motivation is divided into two different categories. We classically name them "intrinsic" motivation — explains that people, who have this type of motivation in their life, enjoy doing something with an interest for just their pleasure, without intending any extra benefits — and

"extrinsic" refers to people who make or do something after aiming at getting worthwhile outcomes, like rewards, money, promotion, etc [Ryan & Deci, 2000:54-55].

Digital Games and Motivation in EFL

Conducting lessons with a class that embraces students whose motives are quite distinct can be a challenging task for teachers; for this reason, educators should use interactive and engaging games to run the class effectively. As emphasized by [Wichadee S., & Pattanapichet, 2018:78-79], they carried out quantitative research about using the digital game "Kahoot" in English language classes to check whether it can enhance students' motivation and engagement. The results revealed a statistically significant difference between control and experimental groups in regard to their motivation and interest level at 0.05. It can be understood that competence-based interesting games can rise intrinsic motivation of students by stimulating them to win the game with full of joy during the lessons.

Teachers' role in education

Teachers are always seen as a facilitator, instructor and knowledge-provider, nevertheless, they are real life motivators and psychologists when they create psychological safety or supportive learning atmosphere for their learners. According to [Dörnyei, 2001:153-174], positive learning environment can have a huge impact on students' intrinsic motivation by helping them speak openly and share their expressions easily during the classes. Teaching EFL in non-native auditory has happened mostly with the help of traditional teacher-centred approach that reduced students' participation, willingness and engagement so far. However, teacher-focused way of learning is not going to work anymore, where student-centred approach is emphasized widely. Therefore, teachers should create opportunities for authentic communication and learner's interaction by implementing interesting strategies, such as, role-plays, group work, debates and peer work. These activities enhance both student motivation and build self-confidence [Brown, 2007:586]

Conclusion

This article examined the essence of motivation and engagement in foreign language classes, focusing on their relatedness and teacher's factor which can establish these two interrelated concepts during classes. During the observation period, engagement divided into three dimensions- emotional, cognitive and behavioural, while Self-Determination Theory categorized intrinsic and extrinsic motivation types based on the students' background and learning experiences. At the same time, teachers' role and guidance helps to shape out engagement and motivation of the learners by combating demotivation, tentativeness through forging interactive games, student-focused approaches and supportive atmosphere.

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